

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Annotation: This article covers the prospects for the development of corporate governance in the conditions of a digital economy in a systematic form in a scientific and practical way.

Keywords: Digital economy, corporate governance, Internet, innovation, strategy, platforms, business model.

INTRODUCTION.

Currently, corporate governance, formed in National Joint-Stock Companies, is developing at different stages of reforms carried out in our republic during the years of independence. But it can be observed that this development, when compared with the evolution progress of corporate governance in world practice, has improved qualitatively in a short period. The formation and development of corporate governance largely depends on the conditions of the development of the market economy, the formed economic system as a result of the reforms carried out, and the economic mechanism of the interaction of institutional units in it is the basis.

OBJECT AND METHODS OF RESEARCH. MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH.

In the current period, in which deep economic reforms are being carried out in every area of our country, "the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, approved by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5953 of March 2, 2020 "science, it is important to implement the priorities established in the program of the year" enlightenment and development of the digital economy "and to develop scientific and practical proposals and recommendations aimed at determining the scientific basis for reforming the national economy based on the tasks established

by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 24, 2015"on measures to introduce modern corporate

The application of digital technologies in the corporate management system, today each leader has become an important and priority of the employee. In this regard, the president of our republic Sh.Mirziyoev says: "of course, we know very well that the formation of a digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, a lot of funds and labor resources. However, no matter how difficult it may be, when will we get into this business if we don't start today? Tomorrow will be too late. Therefore, the active transition to the digital economy will be one of our top priorities for the next 5 years."

Interest in the digital economy has grown significantly due to the significant changes that have occurred in society and the economy. Modern technologies and platforms have helped businesses and individuals cut costs at the expense of minimizing personal communication with customers, partners and government organizations, as well as providing an opportunity to facilitate interaction more quickly and easily. The result was a network resource-based, digital or electronic economy. The word " digitization " is actually a new term, which implies the involvement of IT solutions in the process of innovation management and proceedings, and, as a result, the internet provides for the use of Information Technology in all systems, from items to e-government. First of all, let's focus on the aspects of the difference of the digital economy from the ordinary economy. For example, the buyer needs a laptop. This is a traditional economy if he gets on the market and chooses it himself directly and buys it for cash. Choosing a good that is acceptable to him through any trading bot in Telegram, the owner of the goods is told to pay money through an electronic payment system and receive the goods through the delivery service – the digital economy. This is to explain the issue through the simplest household example. In fact, we are all already inside the digital economy, taking advantage of its amenities. For example, our months fall on plastic cards, we pay for utilities, telephone, Internet and other products and services through electronic payment, electronically submit a tax return, transfer money from card to card, etc.

A digital economy is not some kind of different economy that must be created from scratch. This means moving the existing economy into a new system by creating new technologies, platforms and business models and introducing them into everyday life .

Symptoms:

- high degree of automation;
- * Electronic Document Exchange;
- * electronic integralization of accounting and management systems;
- * databases;
- * Availability of CRM (customer interaction system);
- * corporate networks.

Facilities:

1. Costs for payments are reduced (for example, a trip to the bank and other resources are saved).
2. More and faster information about goods and services is obtained.
3. The opportunities for goods and services in the digital world to enter the world market are great.
4. Due to the rapid acquisition of Fidbek (consumer opinion), goods and services are rapidly improved.
5. Faster, better quality, more convenient.

The fact that the state has chosen the path to the development of the digital economy opens up new directions in the field of Information Technology and, in general, in the field of electronic document circulation. The turn towards "digital technologies" was caused by the development of the entire World Wide Web and quality communication.

Based on the proposed methodology for assessing the effectiveness of corporate governance in the development of innovation processes in the field of digital economy, the current state of affairs of today was analyzed. (Table 1).

Current status analysis on the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of corporate governance of innovation processes in the field of digital economics.

Table 1.

№	Indicators	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
1.	Innovation communication indicators	6	6,5	8	10,5	11
2.	Indicators of human capital involved in innovation processes	5,5	5,5	5,5	5,5	7,5
3.	Digital business indicators	5	5	5	6	6
4.	Innovation goods and services indicators	5,5	5,5	5,5	6	7
5.	Integral indicator	22	22,5	24	28	31,5

In the table presented, a current case analysis has been carried out on the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of corporate governance in the development of innovation processes in the field of digital economy. Based on the proposed methodology, the current state integral figure is 31.5.

In the field of digital economics, a model has been developed for the formation of a group of indicators that are sources of information in providing information to each stage of corporate governance of innovational processes and are used in monitoring the management of innovational processes.

In this model, the following indicators are used for monitoring:

1. Indicators of the stage of problem identification and formation of an innovative idea:

- taxing online applications and identifying the problem;
- studying competitors;
- taxing the activities of foreign companies;

2. Technical indicators of the stage of development and preparation of documents:

- Percentage of innovation process management concept planning;
- Percentage of development and organization of management concept;
- Percentage of documentation to start implementing innovation processes;

3. Indicators of the stage of management of the implementation of innovation processes:

- Selection of the form of management of innovative processes – formation of the Working Group and determination of those responsible;
- Innovation process control and regulation;
- Presentation of the results of innovation processes to the introduction into production;

4. Indicators of presentation of the result of innovative processes:

- launch demo version;
- conducting marketing research in test mode;

5. Indicators of technology transfer and commercialization:

- determination of the directions of public presentation;
- attract investment in transfer and advertising costs.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the rapid introduction of the modern corporate governance process into the field of digital economy with the widespread use of the achievements of Science and technology is an important condition for the development of our economy. In the context of globalization, the rapid development of the modern corporate governance process in the field of

digital economy in the leading countries of the world assumes the implementation of reforms based on modern innovative ideas, developments and technologies that ensure the rapid and high-quality advancement of our country towards the leaders of world civilization. The fact that the state has chosen the path to the development of the digital economy opens up new directions in the field of Information Technology and, in general, in the field of electronic document circulation. The turn towards "digital technologies" is caused by the development of the entire World Wide Web and quality communication.

At the same time, the analyzes carried out showed that work on modernizing, diversifying production, increasing its volume and expanding the range of competitive products in domestic and foreign markets is not being carried out to the point.

Innovation development strategy on the basis of a complex of interconnected methodological and scientific and practical rules on the management of innovation processes, changes should be made to the organizational structure of the company in order to develop a corporate management system, to adapt organizational structures to market conditions.

Due to the fact that the digital economy covers the whole world, any public project on informatization and digitization should be studied in complex and on the basis of identification of information related to a single coding system, economic and management.

The most important aspect in the development of the digital economy, and at the same time the most complex stage, is the need to simplify the business environment and maximize the cost of spending on the communication of people and business with the state.

The introduction of the above proposals into practice, in our view, will make it possible for the rise of corporate governance in the development of the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and this, in turn, will have an impact on the deepening of the process of shareholders in the real production sector of Uzbekistan.

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